

ISic0720

I.Sicily inscription 0720

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

(?)

Material

marble

Object

stele (?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Deposit of the Roman theatre, Catania?

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493953

EDCS 32701140

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 40

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 177 no.53 fig.

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